

STAGES OF FORMATION OF INSTITUTIONAL INDEPENDENCE IN THE MANAGEMENT OF HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract: In this article, the theoretical and methodological foundations of improving the mechanisms of introducing the principles of institutional independence, the ways of improving the mechanisms of introducing the principles of institutional independence based on international standards, the tasks of improving the mechanisms of introducing the principles of institutional independence are studied. Also, current issues of improving the mechanisms of introducing the principles of institutional independence are analyzed.

Key words: institutional independence, principle, mechanism, improvement, theoretical-methodological basis, international standards, management, managerial competencies, academic, educational determinants, marketing, management, integration, forecasting, globalization, functional, digitized system.

INTRODUCTION. Limitation of institutional independence is characteristic of universities in many countries today. The press often points to the fact that professors who oppose their university's policies are punished, particularly part-time teachers who in many countries are deprived of the right to adequate protection of their academic freedom because they are only one those hired to teach the course. A demonstration of the violation of institutional independence is control over publications, state requirements for educational programs. Institutional independence is weak and under great pressure, which has led to the development of a system of safeguards for its successful operation and application.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS. Among the scientists of our country, U.SH. N.K. Yoldoshev, I.U. Majidov, D.Kh. Nabiyeu, R.I. Nurimbetov, B.Kh. Rakhimov, D.N. Rakhimova, R.A. Rakhmanbayeva, M.Kh. Saidov, A.N. Samadov, T.SH. Shodiyev, Sh.D. Ergashkhodjayeva, A.T. Yusupov, Sh. Kurbanov and others. N.V. Demidov, S.V. Sulima, S.A. scientists from CIS countries. Druzhilov, K.I. Morozova, S.D.Reznik, S.M.Vasin, O.A.Sazikina, O.Bichkova, L.Verbitskaya, V.Kasevich, M.V.Niyazova, V.YE.Varavenko, Johan G. Vissema, F.Altbach, P.Y.Grishina, R.N.Abramov, E.V. Galajinsky, In the scientific works of A.O.Grudzinsky, R.Dim, V.Konnov, M.Repina and others, methodological aspects

of the introduction of the principles of institutional independence were studied and analyzed.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Management can be classified on the basis of various theories and a number of levels can be determined, but from the point of view of practice, taking into account its significance, it is appropriate to divide it into two levels:

- the first level of management - the theory of management consisting of a complex of philosophical, pedagogical, political, economic and sociological concepts capable of clearly explaining the mechanism of activity of institutions at various periodic stages of the development of society;

- the second level of management is a set of management objects, practical knowledge and skills, more precisely, an applied science covering fundamental scientific theories (mathematics, logic, psychology, acmeology) in order to ensure the development of society.

Taking into account the purpose, areas, orientation, methods and techniques of management, it can be divided into general, private, urgent, tactical and strategic types.

German scientists W.Zigert and L.Lang, who conducted research on management issues, defined management as follows: Management is a type of management of people and the use of funds that ensures the achievement of the set goal humanely, economically and rationally. From the point of view of the American scientist P. Drucker, management is an intangible type of activity that transforms the crowd into an effective, goal-oriented and productive group. Management levels are generally divided into three main categories:

1. Institutional stage;
2. Management stage;
3. Technical stage.

Let's look at them:

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References:

1. Altrichler, H. (2001): The Reflective Practitioner. In: Journal für Lehrerinnen- und Lehrerbildung, H.2. — S. 56—60.
2. Incheon Declaration Education 2030: Towards inclusive and equitable quality education and lifelong learning for all (World Education Forum, 19-22 may 2015, Incheon, Republic of Korea).
3. Bush, T. (2003) Theories of Educational Leadership and Management. 3rd edn. London: Sage.; Clark, B.R. (1983a). The Higher Education System. Berkeley: University of California Press
4. Valentine, J. W., & Prater, M. (2011). Instructional, transformational, and managerial leadership and student achievement: High school principals make a difference. NASSP Bulletin, 0192636511404062.
5. Sandhya Khedekar. Educational Management, TSCER. III.1 Function of Education Management. 2007. P. 1.
6. 6. Kambarov J.Kh., Turdalieva M.M. Issues of improving quality control of education in higher education institutions. Journal of modern education. 2014. No. 7. -B. 19.
7. 7. Mukhtorov A, Sultanov T. Foreign experiences on the development of the field of education// Scientific electronic magazine of Economy and innovative technologies. No. 4, May, 2012. -B.2.

